

FROM THE LIFE OF SURKHANDARYA BUILDERS

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Abstract: It is not a secret that in recent years special attention has been paid to the development of the construction industry in Uzbekistan. As a result of the decrees and decisions of the government and the head of state aimed at further improving the system, the adopted state programs, ensuring their implementation, and the measures being taken to improve the effectiveness of reforms in the network, the scope of creativity is expanding. The article presents scenes from the lives of some Surkhondaryya builders.

Keywords: builder, Surkhondaryo, Kudrat Jumayevich Gurbaniozov, Bahadir Karshiyevich Nazarov, Erkin Omonovich Norqabilov, "Kishloq Kurilish Invest" Limited Liability Company.

Аннотация: Не секрет, что в последние годы развитию строительной отрасли в Узбекистане уделяется особое внимание. В результате постановлений и решений правительства и главы государства, направленных на дальнейшее совершенствование системы, принятых государственных программ, обеспечения их реализации, а также принимаемых мер по повышению эффективности реформ в сети, объемы творчества расширяется. В статье представлены сцены из жизни некоторых сурхандарьинских строителей.

Ключевые слова: строитель, Сурхандарьинская область, Кудрат Джумаевич Гурбанизов, Бахадир Каршиевич Назаров, Эркин Омонович Норгабиллов, Общество с ограниченной ответственностью «Кишлок Курилиш Инвест».

Kudrat Jumayevich Gurbaniozov was born on May 13, 1960 in Shorchi district in the house of father Juma Gurbaniozov (1931-1961) and mother Zarkhol Mamataliyeva (1934). He returned from military service in 1979-1981. In 1981-1987, he worked as a welder at the Tashkent tractor plant, in 1987-1991, he worked as an instructor of the youth committee of Altinsoy district and as a manager of the finance branch. In 1991-1995, he was the manager of the Surkhondaryya region fruit and vegetable and viticulture production association, in 1995-2000 he was the head of the general department of the Surkhondaryya region specialized joint-stock business "Mevasabzavotbank", the head of archives, the 1st category specialist of the securities branch, in 2000-2002 he

was the head of the general department of the specialized joint-stock company "Mevasabzavotbank" of the Surkhondarya region, in 2000-2002 Savdogarbank worked as the leading specialist of the money circulation and securities department, chief specialist of the credit and economic analysis and money circulation department of the Surkhondarya region branch. In 2002-2003, the leading specialist of the money circulation department of the Surkhondarya regional branch of the joint-stock commercial "G'allabank", in 2003, the head of the cash circulation department of the Surkhondarya regional branch of the joint-stock commercial "Gallabank", in 2003-2009, the head of the credit department of the Surkhondaryo regional branch of the joint-stock commercial "Gallabank". specialist. In 2009-2013, the director of the Surkhondarya branch of the specialized branch engineering company "Kishloq Kurilish Invest", in 2013-2016, the deputy director of the Surkhondarya branch of the engineering company of the limited liability company "Kishloq Kurilish Invest", in 2016-2017, the engineering company of the limited liability company "Kishloq Kurilish Invest" In 2017-2018, he worked as the director of the Surkhondarya branch. In 2017-2018, he was the head of the "Construction financing and business contracts" department of the engineering company "Kishloq Kurilish Invest" Limited Liability Company, from 2018 to the present, he was the acting director of the Surkhondarya branch of the engineering company "Kishloq Kurilish Invest" Limited Liability Company. is working. Married. Together with his wife Ashirgul Sattorovna Safarova (1969), they are raising three children (two boys and one girl).

Bahadir Karshiyevich Nazarov was born on March 5, 1967 in Shorchi district to the family of father Karshi Nazarov (1933-2003) and mother Zulayho Nazarova (1946). In 1984-1985, he worked as a disinfectant at the Kumkurgan District State Sanitary Epidemiology Department, and in 1985-1991, he was a student of the Tashkent Polytechnic Institute. He returned from military service in 1986-1988. In 1991-1992 he was a student of the Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction, in 1992-1994 he was a special management technician in the economic accounts of the Trust "Surkhansuvkurilish" of Termiz city (in the Republic of Afghanistan), in 1994-2008 he was a supervisor of the open joint-stock company "Surkhan Kombinati" of Kumkurgan district, engineer-technologist, the head of the laboratory and technical control department, in 2008-2009 worked effectively as a laboratory engineer and chief specialist of the State Architectural and Construction Control Inspection of Surkhondarya region. In 2009-2015, he was the leading specialist and chief

specialist of the Department of Standardization and Certification of Construction Products of the Surkhondarya Region State Architecture and Construction Control Inspection, in 2015-2016, he was the head of the secretariat of the first deputy of the governor of Surkhondarya Region for capital construction, communications, communal economy and improvement issues, in 2016- In 2017, he worked as the head of the laboratory of the State Architecture and Construction Control Inspection of Surkhondarya Region, and from 2017 to the present, he was acting as the head of the State Architecture and Construction Control Inspection of Surkhondarya Region. Together with his wife Muhabbat Davlatovna Abdullayeva (1974), they are raising three children (two girls and one boy).

Erkin Omonovich Norqabilov was born on July 25, 1970 in the family of Yangariq community farm, Termiz district, Surkhondarya region, in the family of father Buzrukvari Omon Norqabilov and mother Baharoy Doniyorova. In 1990-1992, he was the manager of store No. 27 of the Yangariq Matlubot Society, in 1992-1994 he was the manager of the No. 2 store belonging to the Yangariq Matlubot Society, in 1994-1997 he was the manager of the accounting department of the Termiz Agricultural Technical College, in 1994-1996 he was the manager of the No. 7 store under the Yangariq Matlubot Society. In 1996-1997, he worked as a manager of the store No. 6 belonging to the Yangariq Matlubot Society, and in 1997-2001, he worked as a director of the Yangariq trade and production enterprise. In 2001-2002, he was the head of the sales and marketing department at Termiz Food Supply Subsidiary Company, in 2002-2003 he was the head of the sales and marketing department of "Termizgoshtsutsavdo" open joint-stock company, in 2003 he was the faculty of economics of Termiz State University, in 2003-2006 he was a subsidiary of "Termizsanoatmollari". the director of the enterprise, from 2006 to September 29, 2012, the director of the fruit and vegetable production and packaging enterprise of the joint-stock company "Surkhondarya Food Goods", in 2007, the Faculty of Law of the National University of Uzbekistan, from October 1, 2012, the deputy head of the farm "Surkhan Sarvari", Termiz district worked in the position. Married. Together with his wife Nasiba Togayeva, they raised three daughters and one son.

Hayitali Mamadalievich Allamurodov, who has been making a worthy contribution to the construction of the Surkhan oasis. He was born on September 10, 1967 in Boysun district, Surkhondarya region, in the family of father Mamadali Allamurodov and mother Rozikhol Saidova. Hayitalini, who was

interested in nature from a young age, was fascinated by the great miracles created by nature, so she tried to achieve her dreams, she tried to use her energy to make some great discoveries. He created buildings the size of mountains and hastened to rebuild his village on the basis of these buildings. Service to people always attracts him to new goals, he tries to get people's blessings by whatever means, and because of this, he first started trading. Because of this, at first he served as the manager of the Termiz city matlubot trade enterprise in 1985-1996, and as the director of the private firm "Everest" in the period 1996-2006. However, dreams of the navel blood spilled in his native village in his youth did not give him peace. In order to achieve this, he seriously began to realize that it is necessary to work as an independent leader, not an independent organization, in order to independently realize his ideas. As a result, the initial efforts, albeit with difficulty, began to manifest their ways in a creative and positive way. At a time when many people did not yet understand that happiness comes to a person from the unseen, from the sight of God, Hayitali understood that it is not necessary to study somewhere, but to have the ability given by our Creator to make dreams come true. In spite of the obstacles, in spite of the pressures on him when starting the work, he started to build decent houses for our people without fear or hesitation. From 2006 to 2012, Hayitali worked as the director of the private firm "Muhammadali" of Termiz city, and from 2012 to the present, he worked as the general director of the specialized repair and construction organization of Termiz city "Termiz-tezkor-kurilish". As time goes by, new generations will definitely imagine who built these buildings, the beauty, beauty, and grandeur of the buildings will be admired by everyone. Hayitali is creating buildings that will last for centuries, which is an expression of his perfect, generous, patient, generous, modest, modest, and boundless devotion to his profession. Married. Together with his wife Salomat Hasanova, they are raising two sons and two daughters. People who are worthy of the pages of history will be remembered by history for a long time, their works, professions, services to the country and people will live forever. Haiytalini's services in the great constructions being carried out in our new Uzbekistan are endless, and our people and country are grateful for that.

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